

SYNTHESIS OF NICKEL ACRYLATE COPOLYMER

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Annotation: In this work, the composition, structure, approximate structural formulas, physicochemical properties, and viscosity of a metal-containing copolymer based on acrylic acid are proved on the basis of IR and thermal analysis. It was found that the copolymer obtained as a result of the synthesis can be used in practice in the production of dyes and films.

Key words: acrylic acid, methyl methacrylate, alkali, distilled water, crystalline hydrate of nickel (II) chloride, benzoyl peroxide, viscometer, polymerization, IR spectroscopy, derivatogram.

СИНТЕЗ АКРИЛАТНОГО СОПОЛИМЕРА НИКЕЛЯ.

Аннотация: В данной работе состав, структура, примерные структурные формулы, физико-химические свойства, вязкость металлсодержащего сополимера на основе акриловой кислоты доказаны на основе ИК- и термического анализа. Было обнаружено, что полученный в результате синтеза сополимер может быть использован на практике при производстве красителей и пленок.

Ключевые слова: акриловая кислота, метилметакрилат, щелочь, дистиллированная вода, кристаллогидрат хлорида никеля (II), пероксид бензоила, вискозиметр, полимеризация, ИК-спектроскопия, дериватограмма.

Enter. Copolymers are very important in nature, in our life, in technology, and in industry. As the reactions progress, the composition of the resulting copolymers constantly changes, because the active monomer reacts more and the copolymer is enriched with it. In the monomer mixture, on the contrary, the molar fraction of the active component decreases. As this reaction deepens, a copolymer of various composition is formed [1]. There is information on the properties of metal organic polymers containing metal in acrylic acid (AA) and methyl methacrylate (MMA) copolymers and their practical application [2]. Acrylic copolymers are used as a film-forming base in paints for various constructions (galvanized metal, black metal, slate). Paints based on it are characterized by good adhesion and high performance characteristics [3]. Acrylic polymers are used in various fields, in particular, in the production of paints and varnishes, as film and thickening agents [4-5]. Since its appearance on the paint and varnish market, the synthesis composition and technologies of acrylic polymers have been constantly improved in accordance with modern requirements, and are currently replacing other film-forming agents traditionally used for the production of paint and varnish materials. Acrylic copolymers of various compositions are used to obtain environmentally friendly materials [6]. Copolymers of methyl methacrylate with methyl and metal acrylate, butyl methacrylate, etc., the formation of coatings based on thermoplastic, polyacrylates is not accompanied by chemical transformations and proceeds quickly at room temperature, but the resulting varnish coatings soften at high temperatures [7-8].

1698.92 cm⁻¹ region. In the 469.19 cm⁻¹ area, the characteristic frequencies of the Ni-O bond appear (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. IR spectrum analysis of nickel acrylate copolymer

4.56 mg of copolymer for thermogravimetric analysis of nickel acrylate copolymer synthesis. was taken and the process was studied in the temperature range of 20-600oC. The results of the thermal analysis of the copolymer are presented in (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Thermal analysis of nickel acrylate copolymer

In the DTA analysis of the synthesis of the synthesized nickel acrylate copolymer, mass loss occurred in three areas, and one exothermic and one endothermic process occurred. In the first stage of decomposition, a mass loss of 0.312 mg or 9.059% was observed at 189.03°C, starting at 26.26°C. This decomposition is explained by the release of bound water in the crystalline hydrate form.

The second stage started at 189.03°C and ended at 339.65°C with 0.714 mg, 20.732% mass loss. Carbon II oxide is released as a result of the decomposition of carboxyl groups in this range of temperatures.

The third stage was the main decomposition stage, starting at 339.39°C and ending at 601.79°C with a mass loss of 1.242 mg or 36.063%. In this, oxides remain from the decomposition of organic compounds, and from the decomposition of carbon and metal carbonates.

In the DTA analysis of the synthesized product, the absorption of heat, that is, the decomposition of substances at 246.89°C in the endothermic process, was observed. During this process, decomposition occurs due to the release of carbon oxides. With the release of heat (exothermic) observed at 372.65°C, metal carbonates and carbides are formed (Table 1).

Table 1
Analysis of results of TGA and DTA curves of nickel acrylate copolymer

№	Temperature, °C	Lost mass, mg (4.56)	Lost mass, %
1	100	0.245	5,37
2	200	0.312	6,84
3	300	0,714	15,66
4	400	1,242	27,23
5	500	2,56	56,14
6	600	3,241	71,08

Conclusion: According to the results of the analysis of the newly synthesized copolymer with the presence of acrylic acid, alkali, methyl methacrylate and metal salts, it was found that it can be used as an additive to paints and films. In the IR spectrum, the presence of functional groups in the product explains the quality of the copolymer.

In the process of synthesis of this substance, it is used as an additive to polymer products due to its higher porosity compared to other copolymers.

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